

Research Centre ROCEEH
Senckenberg Centre for Human
Evolution and Palaeoenvironment

International Senckenberg Conference

Images, gestures, voices, lives.

What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

30 May - 02 June 2018

Program and Abstracts

Gefördert durch
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**HEIDELBERGER AKADEMIE
DER WISSENSCHAFTEN**
Akademie der Wissenschaften
des Landes Baden-Württemberg

THE ROLE
OF CULTURE
IN EARLY
EXPANSIONS
OF HUMANS

SENCKENBERG
conference

EBERHARD KARLS
**UNIVERSITÄT
TÜBINGEN**

Important Adresses and Phone Numbers

Locations

Conference venue

Alte Aula, Tübingen University
Münzgasse 30
72070 Tübingen

Keynote and Welcome Reception

Alte Aula, Tübingen University
Münzgasse 30
72070 Tübingen

Conference Dinner

Ludwigs
Hotel Krone Tübingen
Umlandstrasse 1
72072 Tübingen

Excursion

Swabian Jura World Heritage Sites, visit of Museum Blaubeuren

Departure from Central Bus Station, opposite Tübingen Train Station

Departure time: 08:00h

Contact

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General Information

At the conference members of the organizing team will take photos of the participants. The photos will be used to illustrate conference reports and reports about the activities of ROCEEH and HEP. Please contact the organising team (ilona.gold@senckenberg.de), if you do NOT agree that photos of you will be used in that way.

We kindly request visitors and participants not to take photos of presentation slides.

Thank you for understanding!

Your Organising Team

Venue

Alte Aula, Tübingen University
Münzgasse 30
72070 Tübingen

Conference Dinner

Ludwigs
Hotel Krone Tübingen
Uhlandstraße 1
72070 Tübingen

Program Overview

Wednesday, 30.05.	11:00 - 13:30	Arrival, Registration and Lunch at the Alte Aula, Tübingen University
	13:30 - 18:00	Opening addresses, Session – The origins of the eternal quest for beauty: What is the significance of Palaeolithic art in history of art and the understanding of the development of aesthetics?
	18:00 - 20:00	Keynote Lecture and Welcome Reception, Alte Aula, Tübingen University
Thursday, 31.05.	08:45 - 13:45	Session – The challenge of materiality: How should we understand Palaeolithic art as material culture?
	13:45 - 18:00	Session – Beyond evolution and history: How should we connect Palaeolithic art objects to the origins of modern cognition and Homo sapiens?
	18:00	Guided Tour – University Museum of Ancient Cultures (Optional)
	19:00	Conference Dinner at Ludwigs, Hotel Krone, Tübingen
Friday, 01.06.	08:45 - 13:45	Session – Perception, practice and performance: How can we access the experiential and perceptual dimensions reflected in Palaeolithic art objects?
	13:45 - 17:30	Session – From digital documentation to meaningful analysis: How can different disciplines and stakeholders profit from digital recording and documentation techniques of Palaeolithic art?
Saturday, 02.06.	08:00 - 16:00	Excursion to the Swabian Jura World Heritages Sites, visit of Museum Blaubeuren

Wednesday, 30.05.2018

11:00 Arrival, Registration, Lunch

13:30 Official opening of the conference, welcome address

Prof. Dr. Peter Grathwohl, Vice-President of Research and Innovation of Tübingen University
Prof. Dr. Dr. h.c. Volker Mosbrugger, Director General of the Senckenberg Gesellschaft für
Naturforschung

13:45 Miriam Haidle (Tübingen/Frankfurt), Martin Porr (Crawley)
General introduction

SESSION 1

The origins of the eternal quest for beauty: What is the significance of Palaeolithic art in history of art and the understanding of the development of aesthetics?
(chair Michael Bolus, Tübingen)

14:15 Michael Bolus (Tübingen)
Introduction to the session

14:20 Ingeborg Reichle (Wien)
The Origin of Species and the beginning of art. Art history's encounter with Darwinian aesthetics around 1900

14:50 Rémi Labrusse (Paris)
The collapse of the origins. Prehistory beyond art history

15:20 COFFEE BREAK

15:50 Thomas Heyd (Victoria)
Rock art and aesthetics

16:20 Ulrich Pfisterer (München)
The primitive's gaze. Art historical and other fantasies about human origins

16:50 Harald Floss (Tübingen)
References to prehistory in modern and contemporary art. Willi Baumeister and Germany

17:20 COFFEE BREAK

18:00 Keynote Lecture by Nicholas Conard (Tübingen)

Females, fish, fowl, flutes and the variety of artistic expressions in the Swabian Aurignacian

19:00 Welcome Reception

Thursday, 31.05.2018

SESSION 2

The challenge of materiality: How should we understand Palaeolithic art as material culture?
(chair Martin Porr, Crawley)

08:45 Martin Porr (Crawley)

Introduction to the session

08:50 Hans-Peter Hahn (Frankfurt/Main)

Paleolithic art as meaningful practice and skilled routine: some rather mundane remarks on the production of art objects

09:20 Chris Low (Oxford)

What can contemporary Bushmen tell us about the art of their ancient ancestors?

09:50 Peter Vang Petersen (Copenhagen)

Amber elks and bears in the Palaeolithic of Southern Scandinavia.

10:20 COFFEE BREAK

10:50 Shumon T. Hussain (Leiden)

Humans, animals and caves: Tapping into the 'more-than-human' context of Palaeolithic visual culture

11:20 Olivia Rivero (Salamanca)

The apprenticeship of techniques in Palaeolithic art work

11:50 Randall White (New York)

Aurignacian material representation: An abundance of new evidence from SW France

12:20 LUNCH BREAK

SESSION 3

Beyond evolution and history: How should we connect Palaeolithic art objects to the origins of modern cognition and Homo sapiens?
(chair: Gerd-Christian Weniger, Mettmann)

13:45 Gerd-Christian Weniger (Mettmann)

Introduction to the session

13:50 Margaret Conkey (Berkeley)

Materiality, memory and the microscale: Alternative considerations in the study and interpretation of Palaeolithic art

14:20 Oscar Moro-Abadía (St. John's)

Beyond art and images. Recent conceptualisations of Palaeolithic symbolic materials

14:50 Niels Weidtmann (Tübingen)

Beyond the distinction of culture and nature: What art may teach us about the evolution of cognition

15:20 COFFEE BREAK

15:50 Thomas Juncker (Tübingen)

Why art? The Darwinian perspective

16:20 Ewa Dutkiewicz & Nicholas J. Conard (Tübingen)

The Swabian Aurignacian and beyond: Understanding symbolic communication

16:50 Duilio Garofoli (Tübingen)

Evolutionary cognitive archaeology and the new radical critique: The case of Upper Palaeolithic cave painting

18:00 Optional

Guided Tour — University Museum of Ancient Cultures

19:00 Conference Dinner

Friday, 01.06.2018

SESSION 4

Perception, practice and performance: How can we access the experiential and perceptual dimensions reflected in Palaeolithic art objects?
(chair: Miriam Haidle, Tübingen)

08:45 Miriam Haidle (Tübingen/Frankfurt)

Introduction to the session

08:50 Inés Domingo Sanz (Barcelona)

Challenging archaeological approaches to Palaeolithic rock art from ethnoarchaeology

09:20 Adeline Schebesch (Erlangen)

The Lady and the Lionman. Using basic theatre techniques to investigate the gestures of UP anthropomorphic figures of the Swabian Jura. An experimental study in body language

09:50 Antonio Batarda (Vila Nova de Foz Côa)

Open-air Upper Palaeolithic rock-art in the Côa Valley, Portugal: Regional particularities, individual self-awareness and social differentiation

10:20 COFFEE BREAK

10:50 Elizabeth Velliky (Tübingen), Martin Porr (Crawley), Brandi Lee MacDonald (Columbia) & Nicholas J. Conard (Tübingen)

The Law of the Land. The selection and utilisation of pigments in the Upper Palaeolithic of Central Europe

11:20 Andreas Pastoors (Erlangen)

Blundering about in the darkness. Controversial interpretations of Magdalenian findings in Enlène (Ariège, France)

11:50 Tommaso Mattioli (Barcelona) & Margarita Díaz-Andreu (Barcelona)

Cave soundscapes: The tuning of darkness

12:20 LUNCH BREAK

SESSION 5

From digital documentation to meaningful analysis: How can different disciplines and stakeholders profit from digital recording and documentation techniques of Palaeolithic art?
(chair: Sibylle Wolf, Tübingen)

- 13:45 Sibylle Wolf (Tübingen)
Introduction to the session
- 13:50 Tilmann Lenssen-Erz & Oliver Vogels (Köln)
Digitized semantics: Decoding complexity of rock art in the Brandberg-Daureb (Namibia)
- 14:20 Christoph Steffen & Markus Steffen (Esslingen)
Digitalisierte Eiszeitkunst. Streifenlichtscanning und Fotogrammetrie zur Dokumentation und Visualisierung archäologischer Funde (Digitised Ice Age art. Structured light scanning and photogrammetry in the documentation and visualisation of archaeological artefacts)
- 14:50 Ewa Dutkiewicz (Tübingen)
A case study for the use of 3D models: The Swabian figurines
- 15:00 Jo McDonald (Crawley)
Murujuga: Dynamics of the Dreaming's data
- 15:30 COFFEE BREAK**
- 16:00 Andrew Kandel (Tübingen) & Rimtautas Dapschauskas (Heidelberg)
Studying ochre use in the African Middle Stone Age
- 16:30 David Huguet (Vallon Pont d'Arc)
The Chauvet Cave Replica Project
- 17:00 Concluding discussion

Saturday, 02.06.2018

- 08:00 Excursion to the Swabian Jura World Heritage Sites, visit of Museum Blaubeuren

Abstracts

In the order of sessions

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Introduction

The phenomenon of European Palaeolithic art continues to intrigue a great number of people and generates an incredible amount of public attention. The interest in this field has recently been even further enhanced by the discovery of the earliest figurative art objects and musical instruments in Upper Palaeolithic sites in the Swabian Jura, Southwest Germany. On 09 July 2017, the respective caves have therefore now been acknowledged as UNESCO World Heritage sites.

Art is generally perceived to reflect fundamental and genuinely human characteristics. Art makes us truly human. It reflects a uniquely human aesthetic sense of beauty and exclusively human capacities for cultural behaviours and cognition. Finally, figurative Palaeolithic representations are widely regarded to reflect the use of symbolic language, possibly the most important trait that is viewed as uniquely human. Within the disciplines of Palaeolithic archaeology and palaeoanthropology, the significance of Palaeolithic art is generally perceived and presented in the context of modern human origins. Both phenomena are foremost viewed within an evolutionary framework: Which advantages did art and music have for our ancestors? Were these elements crucial for the successful global expansion of *Homo sapiens*? Did art even contribute to the ultimate success of our own species?

However, since the acceptance of its antiquity in the early 20th century, the phenomenon of Palaeolithic art has impacted on a wide range of disciplines and fields with very different theoretical perspectives, orientations and views. Within the wider field of the humanities and social sciences as well as the public sphere, it has also shaped the notion of 'art' itself and has affected in complex ways the understanding of humanity's past and present, notions of time and progress, and the definition of humanity itself. Palaeolithic art has also intrigued many artists in their engagement with the breadth and depth of creative aspects of the human experience. Consequently, art historians continue to return to Palaeolithic art to reflect on the idea of a global 'art history', its time depth and its applicability across cultural boundaries.

The discovery and interpretation of European Palaeolithic art has certainly influenced the perception of humanity's past and present in different ways. Similarly, the understanding and assessment of Palaeolithic art is linked in complex ways to a wide range of orientations and notions that have a long and complex intellectual history. These exchanges continue to participate implicitly and explicitly in the establishment of some foundational aspects of modern thought, the definition of basic features of humanity and humanity's origins.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

The symposium is aimed at exploring these aspects by initiating a series of meaningful conversations across a number of relevant disciplinary boundaries. The aim is to bring together a range of perspectives to explore different answers to the question: **“What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?”**

Organisation and structure

In relation to the topic of the interpretation and understanding of Palaeolithic art, the intended symposium is aimed at critically exploring the mutual influences between Palaeolithic archaeology, palaeoanthropology, art history, literary/cultural studies, philosophy, social/cultural anthropology and digitization methodologies. The symposium is particularly focused on critically engaging with foundational interpretative frameworks, concepts and ideas.

The conference will consist of five discussion panels that will address different interrelated aspects of the theme of the meeting: What can we learn from Palaeolithic art? The panels will consist of 4-5 speakers each, who will provide short presentations (15 minutes each), followed by an equally long discussion period (15 minutes). Each session will conclude with a longer panel discussion.

Session 1

The origins of the eternal quest for beauty: What is the significance of Palaeolithic art in history of art and the understanding of the development of aesthetics?

Art historians have been intrigued and puzzled by the antiquity and complexity of Palaeolithic art for a very long time. In the early 20th century, art history has, however, mostly stopped engaging with Palaeolithic artistic expressions more extensively and the latter became relegated as short prologues of the general history of (European) art. At the same time, Palaeolithic art continued to challenge the traditional schemes of art history – like non-European ethnographic art objects. Does Palaeolithic art contradict or support the development of a global history of art? How have the discoveries of Palaeolithic images and sculptures influenced the understanding of art and its history? Is the notion of ‘art’ applicable to Palaeolithic art? Can art historical approaches and methodologies enhance the archaeological analysis and interpretative understanding of Palaeolithic art?

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

***The Origin of Species* and the Beginning of Art: Art History's Encounter with Darwinian Aesthetics around 1900**

Ingeborg Reichle

Department of Media Theory, University of Applied Arts, Vienna, Austria

In the decades around 1900 the concept of *Naturvölker* emerged as well as a growing interest in prehistoric and non-Western art by scholars from various fields in Imperial Germany. The first comprehensive study on non-Western art that included prehistoric art was published by the German philosopher and ethnologist Ernst Grosse (1862–1927), who presented his book *Die Anfänge der Kunst* in 1894, followed by a number of translations into various languages, such as the popular English version *The Beginnings of Art* in 1897. Grosse's encounter with the "primitive" art of contemporary hunter-gatherer peoples was deeply influenced by Charles Darwin's *The Origin of Species* (1859) and guided by his belief that the study of the "lowest" forms of culture and the "earliest" forms of artistic production would provide the key for solving one of aesthetics' fundamental questions: the beginnings of art. This bottom-up approach informed his inquiry into non-Western art and the art of previously neglected periods, such as the study of prehistorical artefacts, as well as the arts and artefacts of contemporary "primitive" peoples.

Grosse's encounter with the beginning of art and his search for art's overriding principles and fundamental "laws" by comparing "primitive" art and artefacts of prehistoric cultures was deeply rooted in nineteenth century debates about the opposition between the natural sciences and the emerging *Geisteswissenschaften* (arts and humanities). Although Grosse was an outsider to the emerging field of art history, he did belong to the scientific community whose encounter with the artefacts and material culture of non-European provenance put the "primitive" on the agenda of the recently institutionalized discipline of art history and thus brought pressure to bear on the demarcation of *Kunstwissenschaft* (art history).

Around 1900 the preoccupation with the origins of art in German-speaking art history and its margins, made objects and artefacts from a great number of different areas, such as prehistoric artefacts, applied arts, ornaments, and artefacts of so-called "primitive" peoples, worthy of art historical scholarship and brought the "primitive" into a relationship with the methods of "scientific" art history.

Application of the comparative method to the vast quantities of artefacts shipped to Europe from non-European sites or recently excavated European material, led to parallels being drawn between prehistoric objects purportedly exhibiting artistic expression and the art of peoples still living who were classed as "primitive". Such peoples were regarded as representatives or "relics" of past historical epochs, who could provide insights into the beginnings of the art of European peoples while these were still at the "primitive" stage.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

For Grosse the engagement with Darwinian Aesthetics around 1900 included applying both a global perspective across time and space and a multidisciplinary approach towards a so-called "*Weltkunstgeschichte*" (World Art Studies).

The Collapse of the Origins: Prehistory beyond Art History

Rémi Labrusse

Département d'histoire de l'art et archéologie, Université Paris Nanterre, Nanterre, France

As soon as it was invented, the idea of “prehistory” was integrated into the Western theories of the origins and evolution of art. Instead of bringing them to completion, as it had been first expected, it became an insuperable stumbling block for the contemporary obsession for the origins. Shedding light on this paradoxical situation will lead me to reflect upon the deconstructive power of “prehistory”, and more particularly of Palaeolithic artefacts and images on the methods and ideologies of art history today.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Rock Art and Aesthetics

Thomas Heyd

Department of Philosophy and School of Environmental Studies, University of Victoria, Victoria,
Canada

Rock art constitutes a very rich cultural testimony, which offers us deep insights into the visual imagery of lifeways that are fundamentally different from those of people today. This is particularly significant in the case of Palaeolithic Art. While rock art is a highly diverse phenomenon, present on many thousands of sites around the globe, to date, however, it has received only rather limited attention from the point of view of aesthetics. In this presentation I explore misconceptions of art and aesthetics that have contributed to this gap in research and outline the value of closely attending to the aesthetic sensibilities and artistic capacities of those who made, and originally appreciated, these remarkable manifestations.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

References to prehistory in modern and contemporary art — Willi Baumeister and Germany

Harald Floss

Abteilung Ältere Urgeschichte und Quartärökologie / Department of Early Prehistory and Quaternary Ecology, Tübingen University, Tübingen, Germany

In the course of the first half of the 20th century, many modern artists, in search of a basic human language, started to find inspiration in prehistoric cave, rock and mobiliary art. In Germany, Willi Baumeister from Stuttgart, was one of the first, if not the first artist who was interested in prehistoric life and art. Since the end of the 1920s, he visited prehistoric sites, collected artifacts and replicas, built up a prehistoric library and experimented with pigments. We will try to retrace this particular relationship between Baumeister and the prehistory and to detect concrete references in his artworks. The case of Baumeister exemplifies how prehistoric contents can be important for the human self-concept and in which extent prehistoric topics can be agencies for the contemporary world.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Keynote

Females, fish, fowl, flutes and the variety of artistic expressions in the Swabian Aurignacian

Nicholas J. Conard

Institut für Ur- und Frühgeschichte und Archäologie des Mittelalters / Department of Early Prehistory
and Quaternary Ecology. Tübingen University, Tübingen, Germany

Senckenberg Center for Human Evolution and Paleoenvironment (HEP), University of Tübingen,
Tübingen, Germany

ROCEEH Research Center, Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities, Tübingen University,
Tübingen, Germany

Gustav Riek's excavation at Vogelherd in the Lone Valley in 1931 recovered a dozen figurative depictions from the Aurignacian, mostly small figurines carved from mammoth ivory. The carvers of the figurines mainly depicted felids and mammoths along with examples of a horse, a bison and an anthropomorphic figure. Later more figurines were recovered during Robert Wetzel's excavations at Hohlenstein-Stadel and Hahn's excavations at Geißenklösterle. These finds included the well-known Lionman from Stadel and four figurines including a therianthrope, a mammoth, a bear and a muskox or Bison from Geißenklösterle. Hahn and Münzel also published finds of flutes from Geißenklösterle. Since then my excavations at Hohle Fels, Geißenklösterle and Vogelherd have more than doubled the size of the assemblage of Aurignacian art and musical instruments from the Swabian Aurignacian. The new ivory figurines from Hohle Fels and Vogelherd have greatly expanded the range of depictions to include women, fish, waterfowl, a hedgehog and an additional Lionman. In this paper I present an overview of the new and early finds and discuss how the diversity and context of the new finds requires a reassessment of the many interpretations of Aurignacian art that have been presented since Riek's seminal discoveries in 1931.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Session 2

The challenge of materiality: How should we understand Palaeolithic art as material culture?

For a significant amount of time, social and cultural anthropology have not extensively engaged in the study of material culture items or objects. Recently, however, these fields have experienced a genuine 'material turn' and further interest into the material dimensions of human life and things. Some of these developments have been summarised under the terms of 'new materialism' or 'new animism'. They have been inspired by a reassessment of established anthropological concepts and notions (e.g. animism, alterity) and Indigenous ontologies. Are these developments challenges to established archaeological approaches to material artefacts and expressions? How can these developments enhance the understanding of Palaeolithic art? How can the complexities of the Palaeolithic record enhance concepts of the dynamic entanglements of people, things, places and environment?

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Paleolithic Art as Meaningful Practice and Skilled routine: Some rather Mundane Remarks on the Production of Art Objects

Hans Peter Hahn

Institut für Ethnologie, Johann Wolfgang Goethe-Universität Frankfurt, Frankfurt am Main, Germany

With this presentation, I suggest a reconsideration of semiotic approaches to these ancient works of art. Instead of referring from the visible content of the paintings to any feature in the society of the time, it is more helpful to consider the way these paintings have been made. Although most interpreters will agree that the act of painting was quite challenging and demanded skill and resources, I shall not argue that this means anything with regard to the social position of the painters or the relevance of the objects depicted.

Refraining from interpretations that link the meaning of the paintings with the structure of the related society can contribute to gain a more differentiated consideration of the act of painting itself. This does not mean to return to processual analysis that would look primarily at the costs of practicing the artful work in the caves. Instead, it is worth following the new approach of Philippe Grosos, who focusses on the emergence of signs. Paraphrasing his approach, one might consider the painted caves as disambiguation exercises. The caves are places, where the painters gradually developed the distinction between a figure (that is a formal representation of a phenomenon) and a sign (that is a representation by convention). Obviously, both elements do exist in the paintings, and, most probably, in many cases, it will not be possible to determine whether a particular element is a sign or a form. However, in some other cases this is obvious. It is worth, anyway, to delve a little bit deeper into that distinction and to re-examine the paintings under this paradigm.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

"What can contemporary Bushmen tell us about the art of their ancient ancestors?"

Chris Low

African Studies Centre, University of Oxford, Oxford, UK

Criticism has often been levelled at practices of using recent ethnography to interpret archaeological phenomena from remote times. Despite this the practice continues. In this paper I wish to briefly review the sort of claims that are made regarding southern African rock art and its relationship to recent San or Bushmen, whose ancestors are overwhelmingly considered the makers of the art. As many will be aware these claims are significant, as leading scholars of San rock art believe that most San art, and similar art from other archaeological contexts, can be attributed to shamans who are representing their shamanic experiences in their paintings and engravings.

Having laid the groundwork, I shall focus in on issues of San cosmology and healing to explore what sorts of relationship their might be between the art and recent beliefs and practices and the actual opinions of contemporary San.

The archaeologists who write about shamanism and the San have little actual experience and everyday knowledge of San healing. With my background as an osteopathic physician, an archaeological training and eighteen years of working on healing among Khoekhoe and San, I am in a unique position to comment on this relationship. With my eye on shamanism, I will present details of San ways of being in the world and working in the world. I will argue that the proximity between some of the art and San beliefs is exceptional and does indicate continuity yet, to claim that all the art is shamanic is to over argue the case. My argument relates strongly to the implications of our Paleolithic ancestors sharing the same bodies and possibly minds as ourselves.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Amber elks and bears in the Palaeolithic of Southern Scandinavia.

Peter Vang Petersen

National Museum of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark

The Northwestern European tundra was colonized by Hamburgian reindeer hunters, and in the following Alleröd period, the Federmesser and Bromme cultures spread throughout southern Scandinavia. The Paleolithic hunters were fascinated by Baltic amber - the "gold of the north" - that washed ashore on the coasts of the Baltic Ice Lake and the Arctic Yoldia Sea, which occupied the northern parts of the Skagerrak and the Kattegat.

The first hunters continued a Palaeolithic tradition of naturalistic figurative visual arts, and among the stone age amber objects found in Denmark there appear a group of elk and bear figures that, to judge by the latest findings, are older than previously assumed, and which contribute to characterizing a distinctive Northern European Palaeolithic art province comprising animal figures and bone implements covered with nonfigurative ornamental patterns of a magical, protective nature.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Humans, animals and caves: Tapping into the ‘more-than-human’ context of Palaeolithic visual culture

Shumon T. Hussain

Human Origins, Faculty of Archaeology, Leiden University, Leiden, Netherlands

It is uncontroversial to posit that Pleistocene landscapes hosted a myriad of different and often counteracting creatures and forces – that humans were not the only, let alone the most important agents in these “fossil” ecological spaces. Building on recent scholarship on agency and agentivity, we can even say that activity in these landscapes appears to have been *widely distributed* and many nonhuman forces are likely to have excelled anthropogenic factors in ecological significance. As I have argued before, however, this condition has important and hitherto often overlooked consequences for how we should interpret Palaeolithic human life and its material traces (Hussain and Floss 2015; Hussain and Breyer 2017; Hussain, forthcoming). If “anthropo-action” was overall a fairly marginal factor in Pleistocene ecologies, human cultural productions – in particular when they prominently address nonhumans – might simply reflect various attempts to dapple with an essentially ‘more-than-human’ world. The paper takes up this interpretive perspective and argues that Palaeolithic visual culture mirrors the situated logic of particular human-nonhuman intersections. I discuss two examples for nonhuman forces that have to be taken into account if we strive to understand the “material visibility” of the Palaeolithic: (i) animals and (ii) rock cavities. To address animals, I integrate theoretical and methodological considerations from the emerging field of *Human-Animal Studies* (Mullin 1999) to show that the agency of animals was an important motivational force for art-making. To tackle caves, I draw on perspectives from *material agency theory* (Pickering 2010) and conceptions of “vibrant matter” (Bennett 2010) to demonstrate that caves are dynamic and intrinsically active entities that – as “*Cavernes Participantes*” (sensu Leroi-Gourhan 1971) – co-produce the visual art they host. Taken together, these examples lead me to conclude that Palaeolithic visual culture is poorly understood without taking seriously the “lived” ecologies and interactional dynamics of humans and nonhumans to which art-making inescapably refers. The larger implication is that we should cultivate ecological reasoning and “de-centre” our narratives from the hegemony of anthropological factors.

References:

Bennett, J. 2010. *Vibrant Matter. A Political Ecology of Things*. Duke: Duke University Press.

Hussain, S.T. forthcoming. MAMMOTHSTEPPE-LIFE. Mammoths, owls and other creatures: sketching the trail towards a comparative investigation of human-animal situations in the European Upper Paleolithic. In: T. Breyer, T. Widlok (eds.), *The Situationality of Human-Animal Relations*. Bielefeld: transcript.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Hussain, S.T. H. Floss 2015. Sharing the world with mammoths, cave lions and other beings: linking animal-human interactions and the Aurignacian "belief world"/ Als Menschen sich die Welt mit Mammuts, Höhlenlöwen und anderen Wesen teilten – Zur Verkettung von Tier-Mensch-Interaktionen und der „Glaubenswelt“ des Aurignacien. *Quartär* 62: 85-120.

Hussain, S.T., T. Breyer 2017. Menschwerdung, Verkörperung und Empathie. Perspektiven am Schnittfeld von Anthropologie und Paläolitharchäologie. In: G. Etzelmüller, T. Fuchs, C. Tewes (eds.), *Verkörperung – Eine Neue Interdisziplinäre Anthropologie*, pp. 211-249. Berlin: de Gruyter.

Leroi-Gourhan, A. 1971. *Les religions de la Préhistoire*. Paris: PUF.

Mullin, M. 1999. Mirrors and Windows: Sociocultural Studies of Human-Animal Relationships. *Annual Review of Anthropology* 28: 201-224.

Pickering, A. 2010. Material Culture and the Dance of Agency. In: D. Hicks, M.C. Beaudry (eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Material Culture Studies*, pp. 191-208. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

The apprenticeship of techniques in Palaeolithic art works

Olivia Rivero

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This work presents the results of microscopical and statistical analyses of Cantabrian and Pyrenean portable and rock art. This study focuses on particular technical traces created by the act of engraving and identified through microscopic analysis with SEM and digital microscopes in the case of rock art. A quantitative estimation of the technical aptitude of the engraver has been carried out. Some traces considered as accidents or errors in the tracing were counted negatively, whereas others reflecting control of the tool and proficiency in the use of various techniques were counted positively. A multivariate analysis based on this quantitative index, along with criteria including the type of medium was conducted using Correspondence Factor Analysis and completed with statistical tests. The analysis clearly distinguishes three groups of pieces: those with a negative index, those that present a low positive index resulting from a balance between positive and negative traces, and those with a highly positive index. These different categories of pieces may be tentatively assigned to different levels of skill in tool control and engraving techniques. The mean value of the technical index seems to be correlated with the type of medium and differs significantly in the various sites studied in the corpus. These data allow us to pose some hypotheses concerning the transmission of knowledge in Palaeolithic societies, such as different functionality of sites based on their production of decorated objects.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Aurignacian material representation: an abundance of new evidence from SW France

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The widely publicized new finds of Aurignacian art from Chauvet, from the Swabian Jura and from as far afield as Pesterța Coliboaia in Romania, have led us to return to the rich corpus of Aurignacian wall painting, engraving, bas-relief sculpture and personal ornamentation that was recognized and studied before World War I in SW France. Scientific knowledge of the chronological and cultural context of that early-discovered record of representation has been limited by the crude archaeological methods of that pioneering era, and the dispersal of many of the works discovered.

Recent excavations at some of the classic Aurignacian sites, combined with the study of archival records, long-forgotten museum collections and even backdirt, contribute precious new data to an understanding of chronology, and geographic variation, subjects, techniques and socio-spatial context of the earliest graphic, plastic and corporal representations in SW France. The sites concerned (Abri Castanet, Abri Blanchard, Abri Cellier, La Souquette, Isturitz and Brassempouy) are among the most prolific sources of Upper Palaeolithic material representations in all of Eurasia.

Following White (1992) we eschew the use of the term "art", and we combine painting, engraving, sculpture and personal ornaments into what we call material forms of representation. Being anthropologists, we do not subscribe to traditional art historical distinctions and categories such as decorative art versus fine art, art versus craft and so on. Our orientation is toward understanding the cultural logic and organization underlying the material construction of meaningful forms.

In this presentation, we focus on the following observations and analyses:

1. The chronology of material representation in the classic Vézère sites is conditioned by taphonomic factors that have removed much of the Aurignacian record in the period from ca. 41ky to 38ky BP (cal). The sudden appearance of art assemblages in the Early Aurignacian may thus be illusory.
2. At Isturitz and Sous-le-Roc, where Protoaurignacian levels dated to 41-40ky are well preserved, shell, amber (at Isturitz) and stone ornaments abound.
3. Our known sample of Early Aurignacian images and ornaments is terribly incomplete, with many important objects having been dispersed, left in the backdirt or simply abandoned on site without subsequent publication. Our research has added 46 new engraved, painted or otherwise modified limestone blocks from Castanet, Blanchard, La Souquette alone.
4. Our meticulous excavations reveal important inter-site and inter-level variation in the numbers of representational objects.
5. At sites where images and ornaments are abundant, they were quotidian in context, associated with all the debris of daily life, rather than being restricted to "sanctuaries" or specialized "ritual places."

6. While it is tempting to think that the abundant presence of heat-treated colorants such as hematite and goethite (14kg at Abri Blanchard alone) reflects painting activities; they are entangled with techniques for polishing and abrasion aimed at producing lustrous surfaces on ivory and stone objects.

7. Regional specificities as well as convergences with other European regions lead us to think that graphic representations express both the need to mark territory and, at the same time, to convey a sense of belonging to a wider cultural entity.

8. The construction of social identity and value through ornaments relies on a construed choice of raw materials, often acquired from great distance: marine shells, talc, ivory and mammalian teeth. These share the quality of visual and tactile lustre, artificially produced by polishing with metallic abrasives.

9. Production and use of formed beads are spatially organized. Unfinished production stages and whole beads cluster together adjacent to fireplaces, showing a different distribution from broken ones lost from garments during everyday activities, which are broadly distributed across living surfaces.

Session 3

Beyond evolution and history: How should we connect Palaeolithic art objects to the origins of modern cognition and Homo sapiens?

A core theme in Palaeolithic archaeology has always been the question of human origins. Entangled in this field are notions of the definition of humanity, human nature as well as the distinctions between history and evolution as well as nature and culture. These aspects have a long history within the Western intellectual tradition and form (often unacknowledged) core elements of modern science. However, a range of recent approaches have attempted to move away from this overall framework to integrate or move beyond aspects of social and biological anthropology to understand the deep human past. Can the study of Palaeolithic art profit from these orientations? Is the link between 'human origins' and 'art' obsolete? Is the study of Palaeolithic art uniquely placed to enhance our understanding of the origins of language and symbolic behaviours?

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Materiality, Memory and the Microscale: Alternative Considerations in the Study and Interpretation of Palaeolithic Art

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It has often been suggested that one way to investigate and probe into a particular cultural phenomenon, especially one in deep time, is to foster a number of alternative pathways into the study and interpretation of the phenomena. In this paper, rather than stressing the possible role and significance of Palaeolithic art in human evolution and its often-revered place in the history of humanity, I will consider how an approach that considers first, the very materiality of the remains we consider to be that “art” can contribute to entertaining a variety of interpretations. As well, the possible ways in which the image-making might be understood as “memory work” will be considered and, above all, I will advocate for the possibilities of a microscale approach.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Beyond Art and Images: Reflections on Contemporary and Prehistoric Art.

Oscar Moro-Abadía

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In 2001, philosopher Larry Shiner published *The Invention of Art*, an influential book in which he examined the modern system of art. Shiner argued that most modern ideals and practices of art originated in the eighteenth century when the traditional concept of art split into the categories of 'fine arts' and 'crafts'. Although this system dominated Western culture for almost two centuries, Shiner suggested that we are now moving toward a new system of art defined by the incorporation of once-excluded artifacts into normative Western theoretical understandings of art. Following this insight, there are important analogies between this shift in art history and recent developments in prehistoric art scholarship. In the latter field, recent years have been defined by the assimilation of new materials into prehistoric art and symbolism. By assimilation I mean the expansion of the domain of prehistoric art from its original core of cave art/portable art to include a number of materials that can be defined neither as artistic nor representational (including personal ornaments, pieces of ochre and engraved stones). This paper asks whether the incorporation of new materials to recent debates on Pleistocene art and symbolism marks the beginnings of a new system of conceptualization of prehistoric images.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Beyond the distinction of culture and nature: What art may teach us about the evolution of cognition

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In this paper I argue against the idea of artistic behaviour being a particular capacity which early humans have gained at a certain point of human development and which therefore sometimes even is understood to mark the threshold between evolution and history or between nature and culture, respectively. Rather, I will interpret artistic behaviour as being a prime example for the way in which man interacts with his surroundings be these natural or cultural. The phenomenological analysis of art reveals that artistic behaviour is not thoroughly understood if it is taken to be a mere representational process nor if it is interpreted as a creative act only. On the contrary, art – in the process of its making as well as in the process of its receiving – depends on participation. The artist does not create her object by copying a naturally given object nor by following an intrinsic idea of hers. Rather the artist receives the idea for her creation in interaction with the material, the surroundings, and the particular situation in which she acts. Even more, she becomes an artist only by the way she is able to respond to all the pretensions which she is facing by the material, the surroundings, and the particular situation. This, I will argue, constitutes an example of human interaction with the environment in general. Early humans had to be artists in their handling of nature in order not only to survive but to form their environment. It is this process, i.e. early human's sensitivity to the pretensions of nature, which allowed them to invent new behaviours as well as new tools and, thus, abetted the development of human cognition.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Why art? The Darwinian perspective

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In his famous book *On the Origin of Species* Charles Darwin remarked: “Psychology will be based on a new foundation, that of the necessary acquirement of each mental power and capacity by gradation.” If the theory of evolution actually explains the origin of all mental powers and capacities, this would include not only traits like intelligence, morality or language, but artistic talents as well.

Children sing and dance; they draw pictures and invent tales – and they do it spontaneously, with sincerity and pleasure. Even many adults devote time to these playful activities and if they are appreciated by a larger audience and approved by critics, we call them art. All this is so well known that it is easily overlooked how remarkable this behaviour is from a biological point of view. How can something as wasteful and extravagant as artistic talents and interests originate through the Darwinian mechanism of natural selection?

This would imply that art directly improved the chances of our Paleolithic ancestors to survive and/or reproduce. Alternatively, artistic faculties may have originated as functionless side effects of other cognitive abilities. Finally, there may be no biological explanation, and we observe a purely cultural invention, a pleasure technology for example. The talk will present several biological and non-biological explanations for the origin and function of artistic capacities and discuss why individuals and social groups attach so much importance to the fanciful endeavours called art.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

The Swabian Aurignacian and beyond: Understanding symbolic communication

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The “symbolic revolution” plays a significant role in the emergence of the so-called cultural modernity. Many researchers see art objects, personal ornaments and musical instruments as evidence for a major cognitive step that modern humans made around 100,000 to 40,000 BP, that provided the basis for their worldwide success. Others emphasize the meaning of the symbolic capabilities of Neanderthals and other pre-modern humans. To understand the changes that occurred around 100,000 to 40,000 BP, it is necessary to define the concept of “symbolism”, and what it means in the prehistoric context.

But are symbolic artefacts only useful to describe cognitive differences in being-able-or-not? What else then style and motives can we study? The Swabian Aurignacian provides us with a large assemblage of symbolic artefacts. Remarkable are the numerous markings on organic artefacts, like parallel lines, rows of crosses, or others. An extensive study of the markings shows a complex symbolic communication system at the beginning of the Early Upper Paleolithic, giving us insights into the social structure of the groups living in the Swabian Jura.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Evolutionary cognitive archaeology and the new radical critique: The case of Upper Palaeolithic cave painting

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In evolutionary cognitive archaeology, some Upper Paleolithic creative expressions have been considered to mark the appearance of modern aesthetic faculties and artistic meanings, possibly evolved with the goal of tackling adaptive social problems. These abilities were reflected in the use of artefacts as vehicles for broadcasting internally specified emotional meanings to other people, a conception resonating with Lev Tolstoy's definition of art as "communicating feelings through signs". Furthermore, such early artistic signs have been often considered arbitrary and conventional symbols, thereby fostering inferences about the presence of fully modern language and theory of mind within their makers. However, during the last decade, proponents of material engagement theory and enactive cognition have criticized such a view as Cartesian and neo-Darwinian. They have argued that artefacts are not mere epiphenomena of modern cognitive abilities and urged for the need to embrace a developmental and phenomenological perspective whereby materiality actively incites human cognitive and social development. Within this paper, I illustrate the core aspects of this radical critique through the example of Upper Palaeolithic cave painting. At the social level, I argue, this practice does not imply the transmission of internally pre-conceived emotional meanings, but rather the enactive discovery of how artefacts induce and transform human emotions. Similarly, at the semiotic level, these paintings were not a priori specified symbols contained within the mind, but material scaffolds for the development of new semiotic categories. Nor were they physical derivatives of "fully modern" grammatical language and theory of mind, but rather they constituted the occasion to talk about shared emotions, meaning and (inter)-personal experience. I conjecture that in order to share such experiences, humans developed, transformed and refined their communicative tools, thereby constructing sophisticated linguistic propositions and meta-representations, which they possibly used to establish semiotic reference, and create narratives about emotions. Within this alternative conception, Upper Palaeolithic cave paintings stand as epistemic devices for the long-term development of art, symbolism, and meta-representational language, rather than being the passive byproduct of such a "complete package" of "modern" abilities.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Session 4

Perception, practice and performance: How can we access the experiential and perceptual dimensions reflected in Palaeolithic art objects?

Palaeolithic art was made by people in the past, who bodily and directly engaged with their environments in multiple ways. The dimension of sensorial experience and perception has so far received relatively little systematic attention in the context of understanding Palaeolithic art and music. However, the wider archaeological community has been influenced by phenomenological philosophies for some time now resulting in a range of valuable discussions, approaches and results. How can the bodies of those individuals, their views, perspectives and perceptions be integrated in the understanding of Palaeolithic art and music? Can the latter enhance the appreciation of the depth and breadth of human experiences through time? Finally, can these approaches be theoretically and methodologically formalised to allow their application to far-removed temporal contexts or are they bound to the limits of present subjective experience?

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Challenging archaeological approaches to Palaeolithic Rock art from Ethnoarchaeology.

Inés Domingo

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This presentation explores the potential of ethnoarchaeology to shed new light and build more critical approaches to the archaeology of Palaeolithic rock art. This approach goes beyond direct analogy, previously misused in Palaeolithic rock art research. As archaeologists we are interested in advancing knowledge about rock art and answering questions of who, when, where, how, what and why was this art produced. Our research methods, developed to answer questions about rock art in archaeological settings, can certainly be improved when exploring similar questions in an ethnoarchaeological setting. In this presentation we briefly explore some of these questions based on our observations and experience working with several Indigenous communities in Western Arnhem Land (Australia), to demonstrate how ethnoarchaeology can improve our approach to the archaeologies of rock art and to raise new research questions.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

The Lady and the Lionmen – using basic theatre techniques to investigate the gestures of UP anthropomorphic figures of the Swabian Jura.

An experimental study in body language

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All known anthropomorphic figurines from the Upper Palaeolithic display specific postures: they have body language. Breaking down this body language into discernible basic units might provide clues for further investigation into the nature of their significance.

In 2010 and 2011, a group of 12 professional German actors (m/f, various ages), one male Australian choreographer, and an independent group of four Vietnamese students (m/f) engaged in experimentally deciphering the body language of the four oldest anthropomorphic figurines of the Aurignacian – namely the female figurine from Hohle Fels Cave (Conard 2009), the theriantropes from Hohlenstein-Stadel (Hahn 1970) and Geißenklösterle (Hahn 1982) and the schist silhouette from Stratzing/Lower Austria (Neugebauer-Maresch 1989) – as well as the Gravettian female figurine from Willendorf (Baier 1930).

The method applied in this experiment (Schebesch 2013) uses one of the traditional practices of professional acting to break down the enigma of a character into discernible communicational and emotional elements: a character is understood on multiple levels by consciously reproducing the basic attitude (body language) of the character. The posture of living bodies provides important clues about intended actions and/or emotional status. The universal ability to "read" the physical signs shown by our conspecifics is crucial to any social interchange and communication. It provides the communicational basis for interaction, the establishment of common ground (Tomasello 2008), a prerequisite for special forms of social cognition which enabled new forms of cultural learning (Tomasello 1999).

Body language shows influences of culture and gender, but its basis is a set of culture/age/gender-independent universal elements. This experiment focusses on some of these universal elements. The participants were asked to reproduce the body language of the figurines and communicate the emotional effects. Professional actors are familiar with the use of physical gestures and can consciously reflect and reproduce their emotional impact. They were filmed during the process of stepping into character and basic questions concerning emotional and environmental perception were asked. In order to sidestep any preconceived ideas as to the symbolic meaning of the figurines, no contextual information was given. Neither the figurines' nicknames were mentioned nor their archaeological or academic importance. All participants were explicitly asked to disregard the figurines' gender.

The results around the emotional significance of the figurines were strikingly consistent between both groups and invite further elaboration of the experimental method.

The presentation concentrates on the results for the figurines of Hohle Fels Cave and the theriantropes of Hohlenstein-Stadel and Geissenklösterle, introducing the additional question as to how the individually perceived muscle tonus impacts the emotional perception of the respective figurine's attitude.

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Open-air Upper Palaeolithic rock-art in the Côa Valley, Portugal: Regional particularities, individual self-awareness and social differentiation

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Mostly constituted by engraved imagery, the Côa Valley is the most well-known site with Palaeolithic art in Portugal. The imagery and the overarching themes of the rock art are overall well integrated in the Western European Upper Palaeolithic corpus of rock art. However, the Côa rock-art presents several distinctive traits, some of which will be addressed in this talk. Indeed, the fact that a number of engraved figures took advantage of previously existing natural shapes incorporating them in rock-art motifs allows drawing relevant insights into how the stone medium was used to portray the views, perspectives and perceptions of original artists, often in a superimposing fashion. While contemporary analysis is obviously limited, the characteristics of the Côa Upper Palaeolithic rock-art corpus suggest an importance of the narratives that might have been conveyed and of the immersion of the artists with the material medium. Moreover, it indicates a clear perception of aesthetic appreciation thought processes by prehistoric art producing societies. It will be argued that engraved panels constituted focal points from where meaning was alluringly disseminated to better suit specific symbolic thought requirements of both individuals and groups. This realization pinpoints the central role rock art played in intermediation processes between individual and environment by encouraging self-awareness and personal differentiation within increasingly complex societies.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

The Law of the Land. The selection and utilization of pigments in the Upper Palaeolithic of Central Europe

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What can we learn from the Palaeolithic acquisition and use of pigments? The emergence of symbolic behaviours has widely been related to the origins of complex cognition and behaviourally modern humans more generally. Ochre has been put forward as a key element in the development of symbolic and non-utilitarian behaviours in human evolution. However, the conceptualization of these processes and the identification of unambiguously symbolic items in the archaeological record remains a highly contested field. Our aim is to contribute to these discussions by presenting the results from a contextualized analytical approach to ochre materials and artefacts that emphasizes the interplay of behavioural, environmental and social factors to reveal spatial-temporal dimensions of so-called symbolic behaviours during the Palaeolithic. This strategy is aimed at a dynamic understanding of the deep time development of past human activities beyond the identification of origin events. Here, we present the first high-resolution analysis of a long-term sequence of ochre materials and artefacts from Hohle Fels in Southwest Germany from ca. 38,000 cal. BP to 14,000 cal. BP. Our approach demonstrates complex temporal and spatial interrelationships between a range of symbolic behaviours and the temporalities of different domains of human activities during the Upper Palaeolithic occupation of the Swabian Jura Mountains.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Blundering about in the darkness. Controversial interpretations of Magdalenian findings in Enlène (Ariège, France).

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In the research into prehistoric caves with rock art it seems adequate to accept our reading-incompetence and to develop our viewing-competence instead. This is all the more important because religious concepts and rituals are hardly detectable in prehistoric archaeology – or only at the cost of speculations operating with preconceived concepts of religiousness such as sacrifice or a tiered world (Lewis-Williams 2010). In such a view one may understand the burning of bones in the hearths of Enlène as a means to create a "religious ambience" (ibid.: 213) or the stone tool production in that cave may be interpreted thus: "[...] the power of that realm [the supernatural] may have been 'activated' in some way by the sound of the knapping of the imported flint" (ibid.: 214). In view of such a purely hermeneutic approach there is the ambition to partly fill this gap of testable facts by the inclusion of contextual data from the spatial as well as archaeological evidence. The cave has to be included into the interpretation in an unbiased way, not attempting to contextualise everything within a certain paradigm such as shamanism (e.g., Lewis Williams 2002, 2010). It has to be included just the same way as settlement or other activities that have been executed with the back to the images, so to speak.

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Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Cave soundscapes: the tuning of darkness

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In the last five years our team has been developing sophisticated techniques to analyse sound in Post-Palaeolithic rock art landscapes. Because of the experience gathered in archaeoacoustics, in 2017 we were contacted by the Las Cuevas project in Belize to examine the acoustics of a Maya ritual cave. This experience led us to develop a series of new methods to analyse inner spaces that can be easily applied to the assessment of the significance of sound in Palaeolithic caves. We appraised the acoustic relationship between the cave and its surroundings, the entrance chamber and the other parts of the cave. The acoustic parameters measured included both monaural (Strength, Clarity and Reverberation) and binaural parameters including Envelopment and Apparent Source Width. The results allowed us to discuss the relative insulation of particular parts of the cave, and of the cave in relation to the surrounding landscape. We also appraised the perceived loudness of sound, speech quality of chambers, the degree of sound persistence in particular areas of the cave and the impression of being surrounded by sound in others. This, together with other non-acoustic parameters found in the Las Cuevas cave, led us to identify, for example, an area where entering into an altered and confused state of consciousness would have been easier, an important aspect to the study of soundscapes given the possible role of sound in reaching this state of mind alteration, which is a known integral component of ritual in the Maya world.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Digitized semantics: decoding complexity of rock art in the Brandberg-Daureb (Namibia)

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Digital technologies provide us with the means to handle large data sets irrespective of individual capacities of memorizing once-seen motifs, contents or context. However, to do so, pictures need not only to be recorded digitally but they also have to be made machine-accessible by transcribing them to a 'meta-record'. In our understanding such a 'meta-record' necessarily is an abstraction implying a change of medium: from picture to formalised language. We present the Brandberg-Daureb Database (BDDb) containing 39,000 pictures of prehistoric Namibian rock art, in which the formalisation of distinctive features and activities displayed in the art allows semantic data mining across the entire corpus of rock art. Finding patterns within the rock art methodologically has more in common with the linguistic process of 'text mining' than with conventional art history-derived iconography. Such analytical tools enable to formulate new hypotheses about the use and function of the rock art at the Brandberg-Daureb massif on a more structural basis. Thus, we are able to establish specific gender roles which to a large part deviate from expectations shaped by interpretations based on ethnography. This goes so far that the conventional gender-dichotomy is enriched with an apparent third gender based on a neutral person concept.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Digitized ice age art. Strip light scanning and photogrammetry for documentation and visualization of archaeological finds

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Since 2012, the State Office for the Conservation of Historical Monuments has been working hard to achieve the inclusion of the caves of the oldest Ice Age art on the UNESCO World Heritage List, which was successfully achieved in the summer of 2017. In the course of the scientific work on the cave foundations in the Lone and Ach valleys, the caves were already recorded in 3D using terrestrial laser scanners in 2012. From 2015 onwards, the six World Heritage Caves were also newly documented more comprehensively with the help of high-resolution and photorealistic textured 3D photogrammetry.

In the spring of 2016, this documentation project was expanded. The aim was to re-measure the most important finds of glacial art from the caves with modern methods and to reproduce them as three-dimensional computer models, preserving them digitally in their current state.

Two methods, strip light scanning and, structure from motion (sfm) were used to document the art objects carved from mammoth ivory.

This allowed the combination of precise surface geometries from the scans with the high-resolution phototextures of the photogrammetric recordings, in order to achieve as exact as possible, in colour and shape, the artefacts.

The computer models of the caves and the objects of the oldest Ice Age art found in the project together form an exceptional data collection and are not only the basis for documentation, archiving and scientific evaluation but are also ideally suited to the creation of media content, from print media and web applications to virtual reality applications.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

A case study for the use of 3D models: The Swabian figurines

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Documentation and sharing are evident uses for 3D models of archaeological remains. The ability to study objects without touching them, to enlarge them or to turn them around is very useful and facilitates access for researchers. Besides those obvious benefits, the 3D models allow virtual modifications that can help to better understand the objects themselves.

The 3D scans by the *Landesamt für Denkmalpflege* Baden-Württemberg do not only serve the documentation of the Swabian figurines. In this talk, I will show some examples of the scientific use of those models.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Murujuga: Dynamics of the Dreaming's data

Jo McDonald

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In a three-year project aiming at the documentation of both deep prehistory and more historic encounters across the Dampier Archipelago (Murujuga), rock art researchers and Indigenous collaborators (including Rangers from the Murujuga Land and Sea Unit) are recording vast numbers of rock art motifs and stone features. This inscribed landscape informs on the use of this arid - maritime landscape by highly mobile hunter-gatherers over 50,000 years. The project has developed mobile recording platforms, and a process for cultural clearance of the images to ensure that the resultant digital database has both research and management capabilities. The project – which is also using drones and 3D photogrammetry - is also anticipating the interpretative potential of this rock art data in a purpose-built Living Knowledge Centre on Murujuga. This paper discusses the development of dual-use digital records, with the challenges of ensuring cultural safety as well as scientific rigour.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

Studying ochre use in the African Middle Stone Age

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The use of ochre by Stone Age people plays an increasingly important role in contemporary theoretical discussions about the emergence of modern human behaviour. However, our knowledge about the broad spatio-temporal patterning of ochre use during the Middle Stone Age (MSA) in Africa remains limited. Here, we present a large-scale, meta-analysis of the evidence for ochre use on the African continent. This study analyses ochre from one hundred sites stored in a multidisciplinary, relational database called ROAD, the ROCEEH Out of Africa Database. We begin with the first occurrences of ochre in the transitional industries at the end of the Early Stone Age about 500,000 years ago and follow the trend through the MSA until about 40,000 years ago. Our analysis is not predicated on a specific site, region or technocomplex, nor on a specific hominin taxa. Rather, the results provide an understanding of the spatio-temporal patterning of ochre use from a long-term evolutionary perspective, that is to say, the *longue durée*. In summary, we observed four phases of ochre use, each showing a stepwise increase in the number of localities with ochre through time. The initial phase lasts from 500,000-310,000, the occasional phase from 310,000-210,000, the emergent phase from 210,000-140,000 and the habitual phase from 140-40,000 years ago. Within this framework, we also address the question of where ochre use emerged and discuss its geographic distribution over time. Furthermore, we provide our own interpretations about how the material remains of ochre can be related to symbolic behaviour such as that represented through ritual activities.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

The Chauvet cave Replica Project

David Huguet

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Chauvet Cave has its own replica, the so-called La Caverne du Pont d'Arc. Totally shut off 21,000 years ago and evolving without any intervention from the outside world (animals, humans), the original Chauvet Cave is just accessible to a few technicians and scientists. The public does not have access and can't enter it.

Then, French local authorities, supported by the European Union, decided to create a replica of the cave with two main objectives:

- To share a World Heritage site with the public (Chauvet cave has been determined in 2014).
- To enhance both the cultural and economic development of Ardèche

The Chauvet Cave replica required five years for the design and 30 months for the construction. The total cost of the project (land purchases, designs, constructions, etc...) is 55 million euros, of which only 16 million are devoted to the replica.

To design and build up the Chauvet Cave replica, we put together scientists, digital engineers and artists. We had to invent new methods and train engineers and artists in order to help them to reconstruct precisely a world-famous place.

Since April 25, 2015, more than 1,5 million people have visited the Chauvet Cave replica. They were made aware to such a sensitive and hidden Palaeolithic sanctuary located 3km away from the Caverne du Pont d'Arc.

Images, gestures, voices, lives. What can we learn from Palaeolithic art?

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